

APPLICATIONS OF 3-D VISUALIZATIONS OF OCEANOGRAPHIC DATA BASES

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Abstract - Creative use of two-dimensional (2-D) techniques in oceanographic data analysis has proven sufficient for many tasks of analysis, review, and planning. Often, however, a greater understanding of a data set and reduced analysis time can be achieved by supplementing traditional methods with three-dimensional (3-D) visualization and display techniques. Virtual-environment visualization of 3-D surfaces offers a means to review large ocean areas rapidly as a component of oceanographic data base verification and validation. For this paper, 3-D temperature, salinity, and density surfaces are combined with high-resolution models of seafloor bathymetry and supplemented with retrievable alphanumeric markups such as latitudes and longitudes and point values of displayed parameters. These visualizations can enhance considerably the oceanographer's ability to detect and analyze features within the data sets.

Applications to quality control of oceanographic data bases and modeled oceanographic fields are described and illustrated. Oceanographic fields for the examples are drawn from the Generalized Digital Environmental Model (GDEM) and the Modular Ocean Data Assimilation System (MODAS). Other potential applications described include sound-speed and density surfaces and oceanographic-feature displays for training, planning, and rehearsal as well as tactical displays for overall improved situational awareness.

Examples presented may be viewed and navigated using electro-optical 3-D eyewear in the Commander, Naval Meteorology and Oceanography Command booth.

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper describes applications of 3-D visualization techniques to oceanographic data. Among the visualization techniques applied are horizontal and vertical cutting planes, semi-transparent 2-D renderings of 3-D surfaces, opaque 2-D renderings of 3-D surfaces, and virtual-environment representations of 3-D surfaces. The various representations are allowed to evolve in time.

Oceanographic profile data are drawn primarily from data bases and models maintained by the Naval Oceanographic Office (NAVOCEANO). The Generalized Digital Environmental Model (GDEM), a source of temperature, salinity and sound-speed profiles, is described in Section II [1]. The Modular Ocean Data Assimilation System (MODAS),

another source of ocean profiles, is also described in Section II [2]. In addition to these NAVOCEANO data sources, some examples use the Levitus climatology [3]. Bathymetry is drawn from the 5-min.-resolution Digital Bathymetric Data Base (DBDB5) [4]; and topography, from the 5-min.-resolution Elevation TOPOgraphy (ETOPOS) data base [5].

Using examples from the Sea of Japan, South China Sea, and Monterey Bay, we describe applications of visualizations of oceanographic data to analysis and quality control of gridded data bases and modeled oceanographic fields. Further examples demonstrate potential applications of 3-D visualizations to Naval operations.

II. OCEANOGRAPHIC DATA

A. GDEM

Temperature/Salinity (T/S) models are used throughout the Navy community for a wide variety of applications whenever a salinity, temperature, density, or sound-speed profile is needed. These modeled profiles are used to get a first-cut estimate of expected conditions, to extend real-time observations such as expendable bathythermographs (XBTs) to the bottom, and as input to various acoustic models. These T/S models are essential for range-dependent acoustic modeling. NAVOCEANO uses these T/S models to derive various environmental products. Examples are available on the NAVOCEANO web pages [6]. T/S models are also used to correct the speed of sound through seawater when collecting bathymetric soundings aboard NAVOCEANO survey platforms.

The original T/S models, known as GDEM, cover the world's oceans north of 60 deg. S with a seasonal profile every 30 arcmin. where the water depth is at least 100 m. During 1994, NAVOCEANO began developing a high-resolution GDEM with a 10-arcmin. horizontal resolution. The first was the Sea of Japan, and rather than limit the model to water depths at least 100 m, this model was extended to the coast.

NAVOCEANO T/S models are created using all available temperature and salinity profiles. The primary source of data is our Master Oceanographic Observation Data Set (MOODS). MOODS is the observational data base for the Navy and contains all available oceanographic profile data dating back to 1920. MOODS contains about six million observations worldwide.

GDEM is created by fitting curves to each profile from MOODS. All equivalent coefficients within a grid cell are averaged. Boxes without any observations are filled by spatial interpolation. A profile can then be constructed at each grid point using the coefficients. This results in an ocean climatology which has both horizontal and vertical continuity. This is the method used for the deep-water climatologies that have been developed over the last 15 years. GDEM stores the coefficients rather than the profiles.

The use of coefficients along with monthly sea-surface temperatures (SSTs) allows for the interpolation of profiles through time. For this project, daily profiles in the Sea of Japan were time-interpolated, using cubic splines, from the SSTs and seasonal GDEM coefficients. Another means of producing daily profiles was applied to the South China Sea as described below. The daily temperature and salinity profiles were used to compute sound-speed profiles using Wilson's equation for the speed of sound.

The sound-speed profiles were evaluated for the sonic layer depth, defined as the bottom of the surface duct, where the sound-speed gradient changes from positive to negative. If the near-surface maximum was at the sea surface, then the sonic layer depth was determined to be 0; but if the profile had a positive gradient (sound speed increasing with depth) from the surface to the bottom (or 1,000 m), a sonic layer depth was not defined. This condition is often called "half-channel." If two successive negative gradients occurred in the upper 1,000 m, the water column was evaluated for the sonic layer depth.

B. MODAS

Climatologies like GDEM are designed for applications that do not require a synoptic look at the ocean structure. For real-time monitoring of ocean thermal structure, other constructs, MODAS for example, are necessary. MODAS uses optimum interpolation to produce grids of ocean temperature and salinity based on observations and a first-guess field (e.g., climatology or a model field). MODAS can assimilate temperature data from bathythermograph (BT) profiles, conductivity-temperature-depth (CTD) profiles, fixed and drifting buoys, Multi-Channel Sea-Surface Temperature (MCSST) data, synthetic profiles inferred from sea-surface heights measured by satellite altimeters, thermal fields from climatologies, and fields produced by ocean circulation models.

The modularity of MODAS allows for its modules to be configured in various ways. The examples shown in this presentation were produced using one of the simplest configurations of modules. Initially, a first-guess SST field was obtained from GDEM for the analysis date. Using this first-guess field and the surface temperature observations, an optimum interpolation (OI) analysis was performed, producing a grid of SST. The analyzed SST provided the surface conditions for construction of a 3-D grid of temperature from the GDEM climatology. The GDEM surface temperature

coefficients were replaced with the OI-analyzed surface temperatures to form profiles at each MODAS grid position. This simple technique produced a temperature field that agrees with the observed surface temperatures and has more realistic near-surface horizontal gradients, while at the same time preserving the general shape of the climatological profiles. Observed ocean profile data from all sources were then assimilated, using the univariate optimum interpolation technique [7], into the first-guess field.

All observations used in a MODAS analysis pass through a series of tests designed to detect and eliminate erroneous observations. Preliminary checks are first made to ensure that each observation is within a given number of standard deviations of the climatology, and that it agrees with nearby observations according to the buddy-checking algorithm of Clancy et al. [8]. Also, each observation is examined against all nonsuspect data using the cross-validation method as outlined in Lorenc [9] and Smith et al. [10]. The MODAS output fields shown in this presentation were produced from a run on 20 November 1996, and 2,886 MCCST values, 401 BT/CTD profiles, and 106 drifting/fixed buoy observations were assimilated.

III. CONSTRUCTION OF VISUALIZATION EXAMPLES

A. Surfaces

Surfaces described in this paper were generated using the Flow Analysis Solver Toolkit (FAST) [11]. FAST was created at the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) AMES Research Center for analyzing computational fluid dynamics and similar data. It can be obtained from NASA AMES Research Center.

Topography near and under the South China Sea is shown in Fig. 1. To prepare for surface construction, the positive or negative elevation at each grid point is normalized to the value of the highest point in the area.

Fig. 1. Topography of the South China Sea.

Similarly, the vertical components for the 3-D grid of the isothermal surface shown in Fig. 2 are determined by normalizing the depth at each grid point to the maximum ocean depth of the area. Normalizing to the topography ensures that multiple types of surfaces can be displayed simultaneously.

Fig. 2. Representation of a 17 degree C isothermal surface in the Sea of Japan in January.

To produce virtual-reality surfaces like the screen captured in Fig. 3, the surfaces generated using FAST are imported into Open Inventor [12].

Fig. 3. Screen dump of a stereo 3-D rendering of an isothermal surface in Monterey Bay.

B. Cutting Planes

To prepare for generation of cutting planes like those of Fig. 4, a sigma coordinate (bottom-following) grid is generated based on the normalized topography described above. This is accomplished using a transfinite interpolation provided by the EAGLE Grid System [13], developed at the Engineering Research Center (ERC) at Mississippi State University (MSU).

The horizontal grid is chosen to coincide with the data-base grid cells. The temperature, salinity, density or sound-speed field is then interpolated onto the 3-D coordinate grid using a vertical B-spline. Again, FAST is used to generate vertical or horizontal surfaces color-contoured to the values of the 3-D field at each grid point.

Fig. 4. Vertical cutting planes showing density variations in the Sea of Japan in January.

IV. DISCUSSION AND EXAMPLES

A. Topography

The topography of Fig. 1 is one scene from a fly-through generated by repeatedly moving the viewer perspective. Bathymetric fly-throughs often are prepared with acoustic images of the ocean bottom draped over the bathymetry to give the viewer a better feel for the terrain and types of bottom features. They are used for planning such diverse activities as a swimmer's approach to a beach or the best route for an underwater cable and also for post-mission analysis. Fly-throughs like this one are limited in that the route must be specified in advance, but they do allow users a moving-eye view, even when graphics workstations and virtual-reality eyewear are not available.

B. Sonic Layer Depth

Sonic layer depths together with their horizontal positions generate a surface as shown in Fig. 5. The layer of the ocean above this surface forms a duct which partially traps acoustic energy when the frequency is above a cutoff frequency related to the geometry of the surface duct.

Fig. 6 is a color-coded transmission-loss plot showing the improved transmission range for a source in the layer. The acoustic energy that leaves the source at a sufficiently low angle may remain trapped in the duct for very long distances. Sound from such a source may be much easier for a sensor to detect if the sensor is in the layer also, and much harder if it is not. On the other hand, sound from a source deeper than the sonic

layer depth may be trapped below the layer, making detection difficult for sensors above it.

Fig. 5. Representation of the surface formed by the bottom of the sonic layer in the Sea of Japan in January.

Fig. 6. Transmission loss in dB from a source in the sonic layer in the Sea of Japan in January. Sound-speed profile from GDEM.

Fleet operators need information about the sonic layer depth in order to exploit these phenomena. The variations in the sonic layer depth shown for mid-January in Fig. 2 are not great enough to be readily evident as a monochrome surface, so the surface may also be color-coded to a quantitative scale. A few pockets with a layer around 100 m deep are evident along the eastern boundary of the Sea of Japan, with a fairly shallow layer dominating the middle section. In summer, the sound speed near the surface increases, and the sonic layer disappears over most of the region.

C. Density

The cutting planes of Fig. 4 are color-coded to show density calculated from GDEM profiles in January. They can be combined with a cursor to read depth of points on the planes and shown in animation from a time series that steps them across the vertical grid. Density is a function of temperature,

salinity, and depth. A submarine or other underwater object may be ballasted to float at a selected density. The cutting planes show clearly where that density will take the object, near the surface or deeper. A density isosurface, like that from MODAS in Fig. 7, displayed with the 3-D topography, has good potential as a training aid, particularly when combined with vertical density cutting planes.

Fig. 7. Constant density surface for the South China Sea in November.

D. 3-Field Evaluation

There are many ways to evaluate T/S climatologies and environmental products. Horizontal contour maps and vertical sections are two ways to look at the data. Vertical profile plotting is another. However, the use of 3-D visualization combines the horizontal and the vertical and highlights anomalies. These anomalies may be real (for example, a quasi-permanent eddy above a seamount) or may be artifacts caused by either data sampling, data quality, or modeling techniques. For example, the surface of Fig. 3, constructed from the climatology of reference [3], shows stalactite-like columns descending to the submarine hills of Monterey Bay. Viewing the digital projection with 3-D visualization eyewear allows an analyst to move through the environment, inspecting each feature and quickly noting those which require further investigation. This technology can reduce the time for these investigations from days to hours. Conventional analysis tools can then be applied to the areas identified as requiring further analysis.

1) Sea of Japan Examples

The first examples are drawn drawn from GDEM in the Sea of Japan. The isothermal surface of Fig. 2, color-coded for depth, has not been converted to allow immersion viewing, but time-sequences of successive viewpoints can be captured to allow the analyst to move about preplanned points of interest above and below the surface. Sufficient transparency is maintained for the topography to show through the isothermal surface. Analysts can improve their overview of the 3-D field by supplementing the isosurface with cutting planes. The

surface temperature display of Fig. 8 is a horizontal cutting plane at the surface.

Fig. 8. Horizontal cutting plane representing temperature at the surface of the Sea of Japan in January.

Cutting planes, like Fig. 8 and the vertical temperature sections in Fig. 9, can be swept up and down or across the basin to look quickly at the extent of structures like the intrusion of midlayer water into the bottom layers at about 134 deg. W.

Fig. 9. A set of vertical cutting planes coded to show temperature.

Conventional analysis uses static cutting planes and horizontal and vertical sections either contoured or color-coded to show parameters. Multiple sections in the hands of an experienced analyst give a good picture of the 3-D field, but producing and comparing the sections are tedious and time-consuming and lack the continuity of vision contributed by 3-D technology.

2) South China Sea Examples

The South China Sea examples are drawn from MODAS. Fig. 10, showing the sonic layer depth in mid-January, is noticeably more interesting than Fig. 2. The reason is not a more interesting oceanography in the South China Sea. Recall that GDEM, used for Fig. 2, is a climatology and averages out time-varying phenomena. MODAS, by contrast, gives a near-real-time picture of the near-surface region. Fig. 10 shows a well-developed sonic layer over most of the area, deeper for the most part in the north. An anomalous pocket with a layer deeper than 80 m is evident just south of Taiwan. It is associated with the ocean circulation through the Bashi Channel. The very shallow sonic layer depths south of a boundary that meanders between Borneo and Vietnam are probably associated with outflow from the Mekong River. Lowered subsurface salinity here is evident also in Fig. 11. Again, the ability to quickly step the cutting planes, like the one in Fig. 11, up and down or back and forth lets the analyst quickly examine subsurface and surface values throughout a region.

Fig. 10. Surface representing the bottom of the sonic layer in the South China Sea in November.

Fig. 11. A horizontal cutting plane showing salinity in the South China Sea in November.

MODAS analysis also uses conventional horizontal and vertical sections. In addition, it is speeded by use of the Naval Interactive Display and Analysis System [14], which allows grouping, display, and comparison of MODAS climatological and in-situ profiles. These tools, together with the newer technology described here, provide a powerful analysis suite.

V. SUMMARY

We have described applications of 3-D temperature, salinity, and density surfaces combined with 3-D models of seafloor. Visualizations of temperature, salinity, and sound-speed isosurfaces, cutting planes, and sonic layer depth in 2-D and 3-D are applied to oceanographic data bases and modeled fields from GDEM and MODAS. Other potential applications described include sound-speed and density surfaces and oceanographic-feature displays for training, planning, and rehearsal, as well as tactical displays for overall improved situational awareness.

Often a greater understanding of a data set and reduced analysis time can be achieved by supplementing traditional methods with 3-D visualization and display techniques. Virtual-environment visualization of 3-D surfaces offers a means to review large ocean areas rapidly as a component of oceanographic data-base verification and validation. To maintain the highest quality environmental information, any and all evaluation techniques are needed, and 3-D visualization is a promising new method of 3-field evaluation.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the assistance of Dr. Steven Aukstakalnis of Mississippi State University, particularly in generating 3-D stereo surfaces.

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